

APPENDICES

A.1 Script 1. Questions for employees (FTE, INT, TRA)

1. *Opening (respondent already knows the answers)*
 - 1.1. Name (free field)
 - 1.2. Which category below includes your age range? (select between 17 years or younger through 55 years or older)
 - 1.3. What gender do you most identify with? (select female, male, other, or prefer not to answer)
 - 1.4. What is your current position in the company? (free field)
 - 1.5. And in which team do you work? (free field)
 - 1.6. Please inform your experience time at company (select between 6 months to 3 years or more)
2. *Expansion (makes the interviewee reflect and tell stories)*
 - 2.1. What do you understand by "onboarding"?
 - 2.2. Tell me about what you remember about your onboarding here at the company.
 - 2.3. What was your onboarding experience like? How did you feel at the time? (If the interviewee does not speak, ask, was it one-on-one? In a group? Duration, format, etc. so that we know how it was organized and if there are differences in onboarding depending on the position)
3. *Depth (specific questions about the challenge)*
 - 3.1. How do you rate the onboarding period/process?
 - 3.2. Do you think the onboarding process needs a change? (If so, how?)
 - 3.3. What content(s) presented in onboarding helped you when you went into the actual executions?
 - [the list of contents has been omitted because it contains confidential company data]
 - 3.4. What was covered by the onboarding you carried with you until today?
 - 3.5. Can you assess how essential the onboarding was to what you do today?
 - 3.6. Would you like to make any additional comments?

A.2 Script 2. Questions for team leaders (TL)

1. *Opening (respondent already knows the answers)*
 - 1.1. Name (free field)
 - 1.2. Which category below includes your age range? (select between 17 years or younger through 55 years or older)
 - 1.3. What gender do you most identify with? (select female, male, other, or prefer not to answer)
 - 1.4. What is your current position in the company? (free field)
 - 1.5. And in which team do you work? (free field)
 - 1.6. Please inform your experience time at company (select between 6 months to 3 years or more)
2. *Expansion (makes the interviewee reflect and tell stories)*
 - 2.1. What do you understand by "onboarding"?

- 2.2. Can you tell us what the current onboarding process is like for new team members?
- 2.3. How is your team onboarding process designed?
- 2.4. How do you involve your team members in onboarding new employees? What steps do you take to ensure that they are effective supporters and mentors?
- 2.5. What steps do you take to ensure new employees have access to the information and resources needed to do their jobs?
- 2.6. What are the main challenges you face in onboarding, and how do you overcome them?
3. *Depth (specific questions about the challenge)*
 - 3.1. What issues do you believe should be addressed in onboarding?
 - 3.2. What competencies are indispensable for new employees?
 - 3.3. How do you assess whether new employees clearly understand the team's goals, expectations, and responsibilities?
 - 3.4. Can you see if, through training, new employees are prepared to perform their roles and achieve their individual and team goals?
 - 3.5. How do you measure the success of the onboarding process, and what are the key metrics used?
 - 3.6. How do you evaluate and continuously improve your team onboarding process?
 - 3.7. Would you like to add any additional comments?

A.3 Script1.Usability Google Form Questions

1. What is your name? (free field)
2. How long have you been working on Motorola? (free field)

3. SUS questions

3.1. According to how in concordance with the usability and experience propositions below, rate the following: **(1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)**

- 3.1.1. I think I would like to use this type of game as training more often
- 3.1.2. I think this training was unnecessarily complex
- 3.1.3. I think this game was of easy use
- 3.1.4. I think there was too much inconsistency on this system
- 3.1.5. I think I felt confident playing this game
- 3.1.6. I think this game was too complicated

4. Suggestion questions

- 4.1. Is there any criticism you would like to leave on record? (free field)
- 4.2. Is there any suggestions for game improvement you would like to leave on record? (free field)

A.4 Script2.Post Game Google Form Questions

1. Demographic questions

- 1.1. What is your age? (18-25, 26-33, 33-40, 40-50, 50+)
- 1.2. What is your gender? (Male, Female, Would rather not tell, Other)
- 1.3. Before today, have you ever participated on any training or onboarding program with gamified elements? (Yes/No)
- 1.4. What did you graduate yourself in? (open field)
- 1.5. In which team you find yourself today? (Compliance, GPSU, Globalization, KPI, Modem, regression, Sanity, Smoke, Other)

2. Game experience

- 2.1. Overall, I consider myself someone that plays videogames. (1 = strongly disagree, 5= strongly agree)
- 2.2. I often play games online. (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)

3. Training contents:

- 3.1. Were there any pending questions during the training? (open field)
- 3.2. Is there any improvement you'd like to suggest either for the training or the game in question? (open field)

4. Enjoyment of the game:

- 4.1. I think I enjoyed the game. (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)
- 4.2. I found the game difficult to learn and play. (reverse coded, 1 = strongly agree, 5 = strongly disagree)

5. Satisfaction, Motivation and Control:

- 5.1. According to your satisfaction, how did you feel about the training? (observe and select the figure that most represents your SATISFACTION)

Option 1 Option 2 Option 3 Option 4 Option 5

- 5.2. Regarding your MOTIVATION while learning about the training subject, how did you feel? (observe and select the figure that most represents your MOTIVATION)

Option 1 Option 2 Option 3 Option 4 Option 5

5

- 5.3. About your sense of CONTROL of the studied subject, how do you

feel after the training? (observe and select the figure that most represents your sense of CONTROL)

6. Content usefulness:

- 6.1. The training provided an adequate level of information needed to properly answer the game's questions. (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)
- 6.2. The training provided information that is relevant to employees. (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)

7. Game ease of use:

- 7.1. The game was clear and understandable. (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)
- 7.2. The game did not require a lot of mental effort to navigate. (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)
- 7.3. The game was easy to play. (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)
- 7.4. The game was well organized. (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)

8. Overall training questions:

- 8.1. Rate the game with a score from 1 to 5 (1 = very bad, 5 = very good).
- 8.2. Write which subjects you learned about on this training (open field).
- 8.3. Do you feel ready to start real executions on the training subject learned? (Yes/No)